

Stability Constants of Complexes of 2-Hydroxy-5-Methylacetophenonethiosemicarbazone with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Mn(II)

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Manuscript received 8 March 1975; revised 8 August 1975; accepted 29 September 1975

Proton-ligand stability constants of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenonethiosemicarbazone and stability constants of its complexes with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Mn(II) have been determined potentiometrically at 40° ($\mu=0.1M$ NaClO₄) in water-dioxane (25 : 75 v/v) medium. The order of stability constants is found to be Zn < Cu > Co > Ni > Mn.

IN continuation of our studies on the complexes of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenonethiosemicarbazone^{1,2}, we here report the determination of the stability constants of its complexes with Cu(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Mn(II) in aqueous-dioxane medium containing 75% dioxane (v/v) and 0.1M NaClO₄ following the technique of Calvin-Bjerrum as applied by Irving and Rossotti³.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-5-methylacetophenonethiosemicarbazone was prepared as described earlier¹. Its stock solution was prepared by dissolving the required amount in purified dioxane⁴ (S. Merck—technical grade). Standard metal perchlorate solutions were prepared as described earlier⁵. Sodium perchlorate (Reidal) was used to keep the ionic strength constant. Standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) solution was prepared according to the method of Allen and Low⁶. pH measurements were made on Metrohm pH-meter. The electrode system was calibrated at pH 4.03 with potassium hydrogen phthalate and at pH 9.07 with borax buffers. An inert atmosphere was maintained by bubbling nitrogen gas through the solution.

The following solutions (total volume 40 ml) were prepared and titrated against 0.4976M NaOH. (a) 2 ml 0.1555M HClO₄ + 5 ml 0.8M NaClO₄ + 3 ml water + 30 ml dioxane; (b) 2 ml 0.1555M HClO₄ + 5 ml 0.8M NaClO₄ + 3 ml water + 10 ml 0.01M reagent solution in dioxane + 20 ml dioxane and (c) 2 ml 0.1555M HClO₄ + 5 ml 0.8M NaClO₄ + 2 ml ~0.01M metal perchlorate solution + 10 ml 0.01M reagent solution in dioxane + 20 ml dioxane.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand stability constant, log pK^H of the ligand has been obtained as the Bjerrum half-integral value. The same has also been calculated at different points using the equation:

$$\log pK^H = B + \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1 - \bar{n}_H}$$

Where B is the meter reading.

The average value of log pK^H obtained by the point-wise calculation method is 11.33 which is in good agreement with the half-integral value (11.32).

Fig. 1. Formation curves of bivalent metal complexes of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenonethiosemicarbazone

In all the systems the highest values of \bar{n} are more than 1 (Fig. 1), indicating that 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes are formed. The log K₁ and log K₂ values were calculated by the methods of least squares⁷ using the equation

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n} - 1) [L]} = \frac{(2 - \bar{n}) [L]}{(\bar{n} - 1)} K_1 \cdot K_2 - K_1$$

To check the validity of K₁ and K₂, these were substituted into the formation function for each system and formation curve for each system was calculated. It was observed that \bar{n}_{calc} showed good agreement in systems involving Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Mn(II) (vide Fig. 1). The relatively large σ (~0.14) in Co(II)

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH 2-HYDROXY-5-METHYLACETOPHENONETHIOSEMICARBAZONE.

Temp. = 40° ± 0.1° ; μ = 0.1M (NaClO ₄)		
	Least-squares	σ
	Cu(II)	
log K ₁ [‡]	11.80	0.050
log K ₂	10.33	
log B ₂	22.13	
	Ni(II)	
log K ₁ [‡]	8.66	0.029
log K ₂	9.46	
log B ₂	18.12	
	Co(II)	
log K ₁	10.37	0.138
log K ₂	8.64	
log B ₂	19.01	
	Zn(II)	
log K ₁	7.97	0.039
log K ₂	7.71	
log B ₂	15.68	
	Mn(II)	
log K ₁	6.13	0.059
log K ₂	6.24	
log B ₂	12.37	

system is due to date in the range $0 < \bar{n} < 1$ where $n_{Calc.}$ differs appreciably from $\bar{n}_{spt.}$. If this range is omitted σ , comes out to be of the same order of magnitude as in other systems. It is interesting to note that

the formation function \bar{n} increases very rapidly in this range. The results, given in Table 1, show that the order of stability is Zn < Cu > Co > Ni > Mn. It can be seen that the order Zn < Cu > Ni > Mn is in agreement with Irving-Williams order⁸. The anomalous stability of Co(II) complex observed in the present study may be due to both the orbital stabilization and change of oxidation state.

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